

CYBERLENINKA

BASE

OpenAIRE

Google Scholar

SHARQ FALSAFASI CERTIFICATE

OF PARTICIPATION

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

O'tkirova Shokhista

TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES THROUGH MODERN METHODS

AND TECHNOLOGIES

DRJI

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

2023-2024

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

